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*CONNECTING ENTREPRENEURIAL EDUCATION AND THE
ENTREPRENEURIAL PROCESS: AN ANALYSIS BASED ON DIFFERENT
CASE STUDIES¹*

**CONECTANDO EDUCAÇÃO EMPREENDEDORA E PROCESSO
EMPREENDEDOR: UMA ANÁLISE A PARTIR DE DIFERENTES ESTUDOS
DE CASOS**

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ABSTRACT

This article explores the connection between entrepreneurial education and the entrepreneurial process, with the aim of analyzing educational practices present in case studies, assessing how they impact the development of entrepreneurial skills and their relationship with the entrepreneurial process. The research was based on a detailed analysis of 25 scientific articles selected from the Scielo database. The qualitative methodology included the development of a similarity network, in addition to the categorization and classification of articles with the help of software such as Iramuteq and ATLAS.ti. The main results revealed a diversity of educational approaches and different types of entrepreneurship, highlighting the importance of an education that integrates theory and practice. The research also identified gaps in the literature, suggesting the need for more research that connects practical experiences to educational contexts. The conclusions emphasize the relevance of using case studies in the classroom to foster entrepreneurial education and better prepare students for the challenges of the contemporary market.

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Keywords: entrepreneurial education, entrepreneurial skills, entrepreneurial process, case studies, teaching notes.

RESUMO

Esse artigo explora a conexão entre educação empreendedora e o processo empreendedor, com o objetivo de analisar as práticas educacionais presentes em estudos de casos, avaliando como elas impactam o desenvolvimento de competências empreendedoras e sua relação com o processo empreendedor. A pesquisa foi baseada em uma análise detalhada de 25 artigos científicos selecionados na base de dados *Scielo*. A metodologia qualitativa incluiu a elaboração de uma rede de similitude, além da categorização e classificação dos artigos com o auxílio de *softwares* como *Iramuteq* e *ATLAS.ti*. Os principais resultados revelaram uma diversidade de abordagens educacionais e diferentes tipos de empreendedorismo, destacando a importância de uma educação que integre teoria e prática. A pesquisa também identificou lacunas na literatura, sugerindo a necessidade de mais pesquisas que conectem experiências práticas a contextos educacionais. As conclusões enfatizam a relevância de utilizar estudos de casos em sala de aula para fomentar a educação empreendedora e preparar melhor os alunos para os desafios do mercado contemporâneo.

Palavras-chave: educação empreendedora, competências empreendedoras, processo empreendedor, estudos de casos, notas de ensino.

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship, as a field of study and practice, involves the identification and exploitation of opportunities, innovation, and the creation of value in diverse contexts (Filion, 1999). The entrepreneurial process is characterized by a series of stages that range from the conception of an idea to the implementation and management of a business, requiring specific skills and an action-oriented mindset (Dornelas, 2018).

In recent years, entrepreneurial education has gained prominence as an essential component for economic and social development, especially in an increasingly dynamic and competitive world. The ability to undertake entrepreneurial initiatives is not limited to the creation of new businesses but also involves innovation, adaptation to change, and the identification of opportunities across different contexts (Gibb, 2002).

However, despite the growing recognition of the importance of entrepreneurial education, significant gaps remain in the understanding of how different educational approaches influence the development of entrepreneurial competencies and, consequently, the entrepreneurial process (Dolabela, 2008).

Although there are several studies on the subject, many lack an integrated approach that takes into account practical experiences and the outcomes obtained in different contexts. Thus, the purpose of this research is to analyze the educational practices present in case studies, assessing how they impact the development of entrepreneurial competencies and their relationship with the entrepreneurial process.

In this scenario, case studies emerge as a valuable pedagogical tool, allowing students to analyze real situations and develop practical skills in a controlled environment. Teaching notes, in turn, provide support to educators, facilitating the conduction of discussions and the application of theoretical concepts in practical contexts. Together, these approaches not only enrich

learning but also prepare students to face the challenges of the business world, promoting a more robust education aligned with market demands (Rae, 2007; Morris & Liguori, 2016).

THEORETICAL BASIS

This section explores the entrepreneurial process and its stages, discusses entrepreneurial education, and connects how it can influence the entrepreneurial process, illustrated by case studies and teaching notes.

Entrepreneurial process

The entrepreneurial process can be understood as a sequence of stages through which an individual progresses, from the identification of an opportunity to the implementation and consolidation of a new business (Filion, 1999). According to Dornelas (2018), this process involves the ability to identify and evaluate market opportunities, develop a viable business model, acquire the necessary resources, and manage operations efficiently and sustainably.

This set of actions and strategic decisions constitutes the entrepreneurial process, which is fundamental for transforming ideas into successful ventures (Hisrich, Peters & Shepherd, 2014). For Timmons and Spinelli (2007), the entrepreneurial process can be described as a set of stages that entrepreneurs go through, from identifying an opportunity to implementing and growing a new business, as presented in Chart 1.

The seven stages of the entrepreneurial process, as detailed by Timmons and Spinelli (2007), play a fundamental role in guiding entrepreneurs through the different phases of business development. Dolabela (2008) emphasizes that the entrepreneurial process enables individuals to identify opportunities, assess risks, and make informed decisions, which is crucial for the success of any venture. Structuring this process into clear and well-defined stages provides an

organized pathway that facilitates business management and increases the chances of success in the competitive business environment.

Chart 1: Stages of the entrepreneurial process

Stages of the process	Description
1. Opportunity Identification	<p>Problem and Need Recognition: Identifying problems or gaps in the market that can be converted into opportunities.</p> <p>Idea Generation: Developing ideas to meet identified needs.</p>
2. Concept Development	<p>Market Research: Analysis to validate the viability of the idea, including studying the target audience, competition, and market trends.</p> <p>Business Modeling: Structuring the business model, including the value proposition, distribution channels, and revenue streams.</p>
3. Planning and Evaluation	<p>Business Plan Development: Development of a detailed plan that includes marketing, operations, finance, and human resources.</p> <p>Risk and Feasibility Assessment: Analysis of the risks and economic and operational viability of the business.</p>
4. Fundraising	<p>Financial Resources: Obtaining financing, whether through investors, loans, or own resources.</p> <p>Human and Technological Resources: Assembling the team and acquiring technology and other necessary resources.</p>
5. Implementation	<p>Product/Service Launch: Introducing the product or service to the market, executing the marketing and operations plan.</p> <p>Business Operation: Managing daily operations, adjusting as needed to optimize efficiency.</p>
6. Growth and Expansion	<p>Scalability: Strategies to increase production capacity and/or geographically expand the business.</p> <p>Continuous Innovation: Pursuing innovation to maintain competitiveness and adapt to market changes.</p>
7. Maturity and Sustainability	<p>Management and Sustainability: Business consolidation with a focus on long-term sustainability and social and environmental responsibility.</p> <p>Future Planning: Strategies for succession, business sale, or reinvention.</p>

Source: Adapted from Timmons and Spinelli (2007).

Entrepreneurial education

Entrepreneurial education has established itself as a field of study and practice that seeks to develop entrepreneurial competencies, mindsets, and behaviors in individuals, particularly within formal and informal educational contexts. This field of study emerged as a response to the growing demand for skills that enable innovation and adaptation in an increasingly dynamic and uncertain economic environment (Dolabela, 2008; Dornelas, 2018). For this reason, entrepreneurial education must go beyond traditional management

teaching, aiming to cultivate an entrepreneurial mindset that values creativity, innovation, and the ability to deal with uncertainty (Gibb, 2002).

Jones (2011) broadens this discussion by highlighting the importance of innovative pedagogical methodologies that foster entrepreneurial practice. He proposes that entrepreneurship teaching should not be limited to theory but should instead be grounded in practical experiences [case studies] that allow students to engage in the entrepreneurial process. This involves the use of simulations, real projects, and activities that promote active learning. In addition, Klandt (2004) emphasizes the need to adapt entrepreneurial education to the specific cultural and economic realities of each region.

In this context, Shane and Venkataraman (2000) underscore that the study of entrepreneurship should focus on the intersection between opportunities and individuals, and that entrepreneurial education can play a crucial role in preparing individuals to identify and exploit such opportunities. Drucker (1985) also recognizes the importance of entrepreneurial education in contemporary society. The author argues that entrepreneurship can be taught and learned, and that educational institutions have a fundamental role in shaping future entrepreneurs who will innovate and lead economic and social change.

Connection between entrepreneurial process and entrepreneurial education

As the entrepreneurial process enables individuals to identify opportunities, take risks, and innovate, entrepreneurial education goes beyond the mere transmission of theoretical knowledge, focusing instead on cultivating a mindset that values initiative, creativity, and the ability to deal with uncertainty (Gibb, 2002). This is essential for the entrepreneurial process, which, according to Shane and Venkataraman (2000), involves the connection between opportunity discovery and the entrepreneurial action required to exploit those opportunities.

By integrating pedagogical practices that simulate the real business environment, entrepreneurial education equips students with the skills necessary to navigate the complexities of the entrepreneurial process (Jones, 2011). This practical, problem-oriented approach facilitates the application of learned concepts and strengthens the ability of future entrepreneurs to turn ideas into viable ventures, aligning teaching with market demands and the dynamics of contemporary entrepreneurship (Morris & Liguori, 2016).

In this way, entrepreneurial education, by aligning itself with the entrepreneurial process, plays an essential role in developing the skills that allow individuals to transform ideas into viable ventures. This form of education is particularly effective when based on case studies or approaches that simulate the business environment, providing a deep and practical understanding of the real dynamics and challenges entrepreneurs face (Jones, 2011).

Case studies and teaching notes in entrepreneurial education

Case studies, as detailed descriptions of real or simulated situations, involve a company, organization, or individual usually facing a dilemma or a set of specific problems. They provide a practical and contextualized view of the challenges encountered by real entrepreneurs, allowing students to apply knowledge to complex and dynamic situations and thus develop a deeper understanding of the entrepreneurial process (Rae, 2007). Case studies are designed to place students in the role of decision-makers, challenging them to apply theories, concepts, and frameworks learned in the classroom to a practical situation (Barbieri, 2005; Yin, 2018).

Moreover, the use of case studies in entrepreneurial education promotes active and reflective learning, which is essential for preparing entrepreneurs capable of innovating and adapting to a constantly changing market (Morris & Liguori, 2016). This process can be supported by teaching notes, separate

documents that accompany the case and are intended for instructors facilitating classroom discussions. Teaching notes should provide guidance on how the case should be taught, including learning objectives, suggested discussion questions, expected answers, and possible paths for analysis (Barbieri, 2005).

The analysis of real cases enriches learning and significantly contributes to the advancement of the entrepreneurship field by providing valuable insights into successful entrepreneurial practices and strategies (Morris & Liguori, 2016). Furthermore, connecting practices with case study analysis enables students to explore and deeply understand the entrepreneurial process by experiencing the dilemmas and decisions faced by entrepreneurs, thereby strengthening their ability to make strategic decisions in uncertain contexts (Jones, 2011).

METHODOLOGICAL PROCEDURES

Regarding classification, this research was characterized as qualitative (Flick, 2009) and descriptive (Severino, 2007); and, with respect to methodological design, it was defined based on the stages proposed by Tranfield, Denyer, and Smart (2003): (1) review planning – based on the definition of the research protocol; (2) review execution – involving the identification, selection, and critical evaluation of relevant articles; and (3) reporting and dissemination of results – through the interpretation and discussion of the theoretical and practical implications of the findings.

In the first stage, the research protocol was established, guided by the objective of identifying educational practices present in case studies and assessing how they influence the development of entrepreneurial competencies related to the entrepreneurial process. Defining the objective served as a guide for the entire process, ensuring that the research was conducted systematically and rigorously.

In the second stage, a search for scientific articles was conducted - through a systematic review on the entrepreneurial process and case studies in entrepreneurship - in the Scielo database. The initial selection resulted in 66 articles; after applying exclusion criteria and data extraction - considering the relevance of themes, keywords, and contribution to the entrepreneurship field - the results were refined according to thematic relevance to the research focus, yielding 25 scientific articles on the entrepreneurial process and case studies in entrepreneurship.

A similarity network was developed using Iramuteq software, with the purpose of demonstrating the connectivity among the words present in the contributions/conclusions of the case studies of the 25 articles. The relevance of similarity network analysis lies in its ability to aid the understanding of the structure of a textual corpus, distinguishing commonalities from specificities according to the illustrative (descriptive) variables identified in the analysis (Marchand & Ratinaud, 2012).

Finally, the third stage involved the analysis, elaboration, and presentation of the review results. The 25 articles were read, and the analyses were conducted with the aid of ATLAS.ti software for categorization and classification. The articles were reviewed according to the methodology suggested by Akobeng (2005), which consisted of applying rigorous eligibility and data analysis criteria. This approach allowed the combination of results from several studies on entrepreneurship and the entrepreneurial process, as well as provided a broader perspective on the topic based on the analysis of case studies.

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PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

All the selected articles feature case studies related to entrepreneurship in its various subdivisions, namely: collective entrepreneurship (1 article); digital (1 article); educational (1 article); effectuation and causation (1 article); ethnic (1 article); female (4 articles); immigrant (1 article); innovative (1 article); institutional (2 articles); international (1 article); small business (1 article); public (3 articles); religious (1 article); social (3 articles); and technological entrepreneurship (3 articles).

Regarding the years of publication, the articles covered the period between 1999 and 2024. Specifically, the years with only one publication - based on the results from the database used in this research - were: 1999, 2006, 2007, 2011, 2012, 2016, 2017, 2021, 2023, and 2024. In 2008, 2013, 2015, and 2022, the research reported 2 articles each year. Three articles from the sample were published in 2023, and four articles were from 2014. The database contained no articles from the years 2000 to 2005, 2009, 2010, 2019, and 2020.

As for journals and their respective Qualis-CAPES classifications, the 25 articles were published in A-tier journals (A1 to A4), namely: 2 articles in *Estudos Avançados/USP* (A1); 7 articles in *RAC – Revista de Administração Contemporânea* (A2); 3 articles in *RAM – Revista de Administração Mackenzie* (A2); 3 articles in *RAE – Revista de Administração de Empresas* (A2); 2 articles in *Organizações & Sociedade* (A2); 1 article in *BBR – Brazilian Business Review* (A2); 1 article in *Perspectivas em Ciência da Informação* (A2); 1 article in *RAUSP – Revista de Administração da USP* (A2); 1 article in *Cadernos EBAPE.BR* (A2); 1 article in *REAd – Revista Eletrônica de Administração* (A3); 1 article in *Revista Brasileira de Pesquisa em Turismo* (A3); 1 article in *Interações* (A3); and 1 article in *Revista de Administração da UFSM* (A4).

Subsequently, a similarity network (Figure 2) was constructed to analyze how the data resulting from the 25 articles were organized in terms of co-

occurrence clustering, which was important for understanding the central structure of the textual corpus of the selected articles.

Figure 2: Similarity network of analyzed articles

Source: Research data (2024).

The analysis of the similarity network derived from the mentioned words allowed for the identification of how the terms are interrelated and the groups/clusters of concepts that emerged from the presented connections. In the similarity network, words that co-occur in various contexts or articles are connected, forming “nodes” and edges that reveal the underlying semantic structure of the dataset, as follows.

Initially, a central cluster (entrepreneurship and the entrepreneurial process) was identified due to its high frequency and centrality, indicating that these concepts serve as convergence points for

several themes and are frequently explored from different perspectives within the field of entrepreneurship. In addition, eight clusters were identified:

1. Resource, comprising groups of articles that discuss capability, legitimacy, and business development, with an emphasis on tangible and intangible resources.

2. Coupling and decoupling, which explores the interconnection between different factors in the entrepreneurial environment and their influence on venture success.

3. Research, focusing on the development and evolution of entrepreneurial practices and theories, as well as emerging areas of investigation.

4. Business, examining how cultural, behavioral, and institutional factors affect business creation and management, including religious contexts and startups.

5. Social, referring to a set of articles that explore the interaction between social structures and individuals, and how these dynamics shape entrepreneurship.

6. Gender/Female entrepreneurship, offering a specific lens on the experiences, challenges, and contributions of women in the entrepreneurial context by addressing both challenges and opportunities for women entrepreneurs.

7. Process, which explores how organizational and institutional processes are developed and transformed over time.

8. Enterprise, examining business challenges, growth strategies, and the impact of public and regulatory policies.

The similarity network thus highlighted how entrepreneurship is a multifaceted field, in which the connections among clusters demonstrate

that the study of entrepreneurship is not limited to a single focus but involves a complex network of factors such as innovation, gender, social networks, and institutional contexts, among others. This suggests that entrepreneurship research is largely interdisciplinary, addressing diverse themes that interconnect in intricate ways to form a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon of entrepreneurship and, specifically, of the entrepreneurial process.

In order to investigate the case studies present in the 25 analyzed articles, some groupings were identified regarding the types of entrepreneurship discussed. Chart 2 presents the article titles, author(s), and the type of entrepreneurship addressed in each case study, based on the 25 articles in the sample.

Among the case studies in the 25 articles of the sample, only article 1 addresses ethnic entrepreneurship; articles 2, 13, 15, and 24 focus on female entrepreneurship; article 3 discusses effectuation and causation; articles 4, 14, and 22 address public entrepreneurship; articles 5, 6, and 20 focus on social entrepreneurship; article 7 examines collective entrepreneurship; articles 8 and 10 deal with institutional entrepreneurship; article 9 explores religious entrepreneurship; articles 11, 18, and 23 focus on technological entrepreneurship; article 12 discusses educational entrepreneurship; article 16 addresses innovative entrepreneurship; article 17 explores international entrepreneurship; article 19 discusses digital entrepreneurship; article 21 examines small business entrepreneurship; and article 25 addresses immigrant entrepreneurship.

Chart 2: List of articles, authors and types of entrepreneurship in case studies

Article No.	Article Name	(Author(s), Year)	Type of Entrepreneurship
1	<i>Social Coupling and Decoupling: pastors as entrepreneurs</i>	(Corrêa; Vale; Pinto, 2018)	Ethnic
2	Criação de empresas por mulheres: um estudo com empreendedoras em Natal, Rio Grande do Norte	(Machado; Gazola; Anez, 2013)	Female
3	<i>Analysis of the entrepreneurial process form effectuation and causation logic: a case study in two companies from Minas Gerais</i>	(Ferreira <i>et al.</i> , 2022)	Effectuation and Causation
4	Práticas intraempreendedoras na gestão pública: um estudo de caso na Embrapa	(Lapolli; Gomes, 2017)	Public
5	Informação e empreendedorismo: estudos de caso com acadêmicos brasileiros e canadenses	(Fonseca; Nassif, 2022)	Social
6	Redes sociais, perfil empreendedor e trajetórias	(Corrêa; Vale, 2014)	Social
7	Estruturas de governança e empreendedorismo coletivo: o caso dos doutores da alegria	(Rodrigues; Malo, 2006)	Collective
8	Atores sociais e campo organizacional: estratégias discursivas e de mobilização de recursos na construção do complexo avícola na cooperativa agroindustrial Copagril	(Sander; Cunha, 2013)	Institutional
9	Empreendedorismo religioso: um estudo sobre empresas que exploram o nicho da religiosidade	(Borges; Enoque; Borges, 2015)	Religious
10	Inovação social e empreendedorismo institucional: a ação da ONG "Ação educativa" no campo educacional da cidade de São Paulo	(Brustein; Rodrigues; Kirschbaum, 2008)	Institutional
11	Crescimento de Empresas na Perspectiva de Pequenos Empreendedores de Base Tecnológica	(Machado, 2018)	Technological
12	Avaliação do Ensino de Empreendedorismo entre Estudantes Universitários por meio do Perfil Empreendedor	(Rocha; Freitas, 2014)	Educational
13	Gênero, Imersão e Empreendedorismo: Sexo Frágil, Laços Fortes?	(Vale; Serafim; Teodósio, 2011)	Female
14	Intraempreendedorismo e inovação em organizações públicas: caso do censo no Brasil	(Gomes; Emmendoerfer, 2023)	Public

Continues

Chart 2: List of articles, authors and types of entrepreneurship in case studies - continuation

Article No.	Article Name	(Author(s), Year)	Type of Entrepreneurship
15	In search of an integrative framework for female immigrant entrepreneurship	(Cunha; Nascimento; Falcão, 2014)	Female
16	<i>Entrepreneurial orientation and open innovation in Brazilian startups: a multicase study</i>	(Carvalho; Sugano, 2016)	Innovative
17	Facetas do Risco no Empreendedorismo Internacional	(Leite; Moraes, 2014)	International
18	Os inventores no Brasil: tipos e modalidades de incentivos	(Barbieri, 1999)	Technological
19	Elaboração do mapa de recursos: processo de apoio ao planejamento de um novo negócio de internet	(Medeiros Júnior; Añez; Sousa Neto; Bezerra, 2015)	Digital
20	A interação dos relacionamentos com os recursos e a legitimidade no processo de criação de uma organização social	(Rossoni; Teixeira, 2008)	Social
21	<i>Opportunity or Illusion? Risk Perception in Opportunity Evaluation</i>	(Massa <i>et al.</i> , 2024)	Small business entrepreneurship
22	Cargos de Livre Nomeação: Reflexões com Base no Empreendedor Público em um Estado-Membro do Brasil	(Valadares; Emmendoerfer, 2012)	Public
23	Mobilizando relacionamentos e acessando recursos na criação e evolução de novos negócios	(Vasconcelos <i>et al.</i> , 2007)	Technological
24	<i>Use of entrepreneurial social networks by women in the travel agencies creation process</i>	(Teixeira; Andreassi; Bomfim, 2018)	Female
25	Trajatórias emergentes de startups brasileiras-canadenses à luz do Modelo de Uppsala, empreendedorismo de imigrantes e da <i>effectuation</i>	(Falcão <i>et al.</i> , 2021)	Immigrant

Source: Research data (2024).

While the "case" is the material students can use for analysis, the "teaching notes" are a pedagogical resource for teachers, offering support for effective case discussions and achieving educational objectives. Given the potential applications of the case studies presented, the following analyses will be in-depth to understand how these case studies and teaching notes can support learning through these entrepreneurial experiences - if used in the classroom.

Chart 3: Case study in ethnic entrepreneurship

Article No. and Case Study Summary	Classroom Use	Teaching Notes
<p>1 Pastors responsible for neo-Pentecostal churches and their social interactions.</p>	<p>Discussion of social coupling and decoupling; ethics in religious entrepreneurship.</p>	<p>Understanding the relationship between religion and entrepreneurship; analyzing the dynamics of social networks; discussing the ethical implications of entrepreneurship in religious contexts.</p>

Source: Research data (2024).

The case study of Neo-Pentecostal pastors as religious entrepreneurs explores how they use social coupling and decoupling strategies to build and expand their "church-businesses."

In the classroom, the connection between religion and entrepreneurship and social media management can be discussed. The teaching notes suggest group discussions, comparative analyses, and assessments focused on the quality of the analyses and ethical reflections on religious entrepreneurship, considering social responsibility and community impact.

Chart 4: Case studies in female entrepreneurship

Article No. and Case Study Summary	Classroom Use	Teaching Notes
<p>2 Business creation by 96 women in Natal, Rio Grande do Norte, highlighting the reasons and challenges faced by these entrepreneurs.</p>	<p>The case study can be used to discuss topics such as female entrepreneurship, challenges faced by women in the job market, and the importance of policies to support entrepreneurship.</p>	<p>Promote discussions on the barriers faced by female entrepreneurs and possible solutions; study the relationship between seed capital and business success; analyze specific cases of the entrepreneurs mentioned in the article, encouraging students to develop business plans that consider the challenges and motivations identified in the research.</p>

Continues

Chart 4: Case studies in female entrepreneurship

Article No. and Case Study Summary	Classroom Use	Teaching Notes
<p>13 178 entrepreneurs registered with the Minas Gerais Commercial Board, 64 women and 114 men.</p>	<p>The case can be used to discuss topics such as gender inequality in entrepreneurship, the importance of networks, and the influence of social and economic factors on entrepreneurial decisions.</p>	<p>Analyze the differences in motivations for entrepreneurship between genders; examine examples of successful entrepreneurs and how their social networks influenced their businesses; and discuss public policies that could be implemented to support female entrepreneurship.</p>
<p>15 Issues of entrepreneurship among immigrant women, highlighting the difficulties they face in transnational contexts and the social dynamics that influence their entrepreneurial activities.</p>	<p>The case can be used to discuss topics such as diversity in entrepreneurship, the importance of social networks, and the intersectionality of gender and migration.</p>	<p>Understand the challenges faced by immigrant entrepreneurs, especially women; analyze the importance of social networks and legitimacy in entrepreneurship; and discuss intersectionality in the context of migration.</p>
<p>24 Travel agency entrepreneurs, focusing on how they utilize social ties in the conception, start-up, and consolidation phases of their businesses.</p>	<p>The case study involves identifying the types of social ties and their influence on obtaining the resources necessary for business success. It can be used to discuss topics such as female entrepreneurship, social networks, and the importance of social capital in business success.</p>	<p>Encourage students to analyze how different types of social ties impact business development; promote discussions on the advantages and disadvantages of strong and weak ties in the business context; highlight the importance of networking and social support; and encourage reflection on the barriers faced by female entrepreneurs and how to overcome them through support networks.</p>

Source: Research data (2024).

The case studies explore various aspects of female entrepreneurship, from business creation by women in Natal and a comparison between entrepreneurs of different genders in Minas Gerais, to the challenges faced by immigrant women and the use of social ties by travel agency entrepreneurs. They highlight barriers in the job market and strategies to overcome them, such as flexibility, social networks, and adaptation to different cultural and economic contexts.

In the classroom, students can discuss the motivations and challenges of female entrepreneurs, analyze start-up capital and business success, and compare gender dynamics in business. The teaching notes suggest practical activities, such as creating business plans with a focus on gender specificities, discussing public policies supporting female entrepreneurship, and reflecting on the role of social networks in business success, deepening students' understanding of female entrepreneurship and its application in real-world scenarios.

Chart 5: Case studies in effectuation and causation entrepreneurship

Article No. and Case Study Summary	Classroom Use	Teaching Notes
3 Entrepreneurial process of two companies in Minas Gerais, focusing on the logics of effectuation and causation.	The case can be used to discuss different decision-making approaches in entrepreneurship, allowing students to analyze how circumstances influence entrepreneurs' choices.	Compare and contrast the two approaches (effectuation and causation); study how entrepreneurs deal with a lack of information; discuss how decisions change as the business develops.

Source: Research data (2024).

The case study explores how entrepreneurs transitioned between the logics of effectuation and causation throughout their companies' growth, beginning with decisions based on available resources and emerging opportunities and evolving to a more structured and planned approach.

In the classroom, one can discuss how different decision-making approaches are applied in contexts of uncertainty, allowing for an analysis of the circumstances that influence entrepreneurial choices. The teaching notes suggest comparative discussions of effectuation and causation, analysis of decisions under uncertainty, and reflections on the evolution of entrepreneurial strategies.

Chart 6: Case studies in public entrepreneurship

Article No. and Case Study Summary	Classroom Use	Teaching Notes
<p>4 The problem of intrapreneurship at EMBRAPA, highlighting the difficulties and barriers to implementing a culture that fosters innovation and creativity within the organization.</p>	<p>The case can be used to discuss topics such as innovation in the public sector, the importance of intrapreneurship, and the differences between corporate and public environments.</p>	<p>Encourage students to reflect on the barriers to innovation in their own experiences and contexts; and promote discussions on how intrapreneurship practices can be implemented in different organizations.</p>
<p>14 Problems of data collection for the 2020 Demographic Census by the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE).</p>	<p>The case can be used to discuss topics such as innovation in the public sector, entrepreneurship, and the importance of adapting to social and technological changes.</p>	<p>Encourage students to reflect on the challenges faced by public institutions and the importance of innovation; discuss data collection strategies and the application of technologies in public administration; and promote discussions on resistance to change and how to overcome it in organizational contexts.</p>
<p>22 The problem of selection and appointment to freely appointed positions, specifically the position of public entrepreneur in the state of Minas Gerais, Brazil.</p>	<p>The case can be used to discuss topics such as public management, transparency, meritocracy, and the importance of diversity in candidate selection.</p>	<p>Encourage students to reflect on the impacts of a lack of transparency in the selection process for public positions and how this can affect public trust in public administration; promote a debate on the advantages and disadvantages of freely appointed positions compared to more traditional selection processes, such as public examinations; analyze the selection process for public entrepreneurs as an example of modernization in human resources management, identifying best practices and areas for improvement.</p>

Source: Research data (2024).

The case studies explore facets of entrepreneurship and innovation in the Brazilian public sector, addressing challenges and opportunities in various contexts. The EMBRAPA case highlights the difficulties of promoting innovation in a public agricultural research institution, such as risk resistance and bureaucracy. The IBGE case analyzes adaptation to new technologies and overcoming resistance during data collection for the 2020 Demographic Census. The third case examines the selection process for freely appointed positions in Minas Gerais, highlighting issues of transparency and meritocracy.

In the classroom, the challenges faced by public institutions in innovation and modernization can be discussed. Teaching notes include critical analyses of barriers to innovation, comparisons of management approaches, and discussions on transparency and meritocracy, helping students apply theoretical concepts to real-world scenarios and understand the complexities of public management and entrepreneurship in this context.

Chart 7: Case studies in social entrepreneurship

Article No. and Case Study Summary	Classroom Use	Teaching Notes
<p>5</p> <p>The problem of academic entrepreneurship, focusing on how information and personal experiences influence the entrepreneurial mindset of academics.</p>	<p>The case can be used to discuss topics such as the relationship between information and entrepreneurship, the influence of family and academic environments on the formation of the entrepreneurial mindset, and the importance of personal experiences in professional development.</p>	<p>Analyze how life experiences shape the entrepreneurial mindset; explore the stories of the interviewees and identify the factors that contributed to their success; and ask students to write about their own experiences and how they might influence their future entrepreneurial decisions.</p>
<p>6</p> <p>The trajectory of low-income entrepreneurs, highlighting the importance of relationship networks and personal attributes for the success of their businesses.</p>	<p>The case study can be used to discuss topics such as entrepreneurship, social networks, and the importance of interpersonal skills for professional success.</p>	<p>Study how social connections influence business growth; reflect on the importance of personal attributes in the entrepreneurial context; discuss the barriers faced by low-income entrepreneurs and the strategies used to overcome them.</p>
<p>20</p> <p>Creation of a social organization from the demise of the NGO "Empreendedores dos Sonhos."</p>	<p>The case study can be used to discuss topics such as social entrepreneurship, the importance of networks, and building legitimacy in non-governmental organizations.</p>	<p>Encourage students to identify the challenges faced by the founders and the strategies used to overcome them; promote discussions on the importance of social immersion and networks in the success of social organizations; and encourage students to develop an action plan for a fictitious NGO, considering the elements discussed in the case study, such as fundraising and building legitimacy.</p>

Source: Research data (2024).

The case studies offer a comprehensive overview of entrepreneurship, highlighting the impact of information, relationship networks, and legitimacy strategies in various contexts. The case studies of Brazilian and Canadian academics focus on academic entrepreneurship, where information and personal experiences shape the entrepreneurial mindset. The study of low-income entrepreneurs highlights the importance of social networks and personal attributes for success in challenging socioeconomic contexts. The case of the Entrepreneurial Alliance illustrates the creation and consolidation of a social organization, emphasizing relationship networks and legitimacy building.

In the classroom, the influence of information and personal experiences, the role of social networks and interpersonal skills, and the construction of legitimacy can be explored. Teaching notes can include discussions on the formation of the entrepreneurial mindset, social network analysis, and the development of action plans for fictitious NGOs, connecting theory and practice and deepening students' understanding of entrepreneurship in different contexts.

Chart 8: Case studies in collective entrepreneurship coletivo

Article No. and Case Study Summary	Classroom Use	Teaching Notes
<p>7 "Doutores da Alegria" addresses the governance issues of a nonprofit organization that works with professional artists in pediatric hospitals.</p>	<p>The case study can be used to discuss topics such as governance in nonprofit organizations, the importance of all members' participation in decision-making processes, and the application of the concept of collective entrepreneurship.</p>	<p>Understand the dynamics of governance in nonprofit organizations and the importance of collective participation; analyze the tensions between different groups within the organization and how this affects governance; propose solutions to improve governance and member participation, using the case study as a basis for discussions on inclusive management practices.</p>

Source: Research data (2024).

This case study explores the entrepreneurial process in a nonprofit organization, addressing governance challenges and highlighting the importance of collective participation in decision-making to maintain organizational cohesion and effectiveness. With professional artists working in pediatric hospitals, the

organization faced an internal crisis due to tensions between artists and administrators, necessitating a review of its governance structure.

In the classroom, participatory governance, the inclusion of diverse voices in decision-making, and collective entrepreneurship can be discussed. Teaching notes can include analyses of internal tensions, discussions of the importance of equitable participation, and proposals for improving governance and inclusion in nonprofit organizations, fostering critical thinking and the practical application of governance and social entrepreneurship concepts.

Chart 9: Case studies in institutional entrepreneurship

Article No. and Case Study Summary	Classroom Use	Teaching Notes
<p>8 Construction of a poultry complex by the COPAGRIL Agroindustrial Cooperative, located in Marechal Cândido Rondon, Paraná.</p>	<p>The case study can be used to discuss topics such as institutional entrepreneurship, resource mobilization, and the importance of collective work in implementing organizational strategies</p>	<p>Study the role of different social actors and their interactions; discuss the strategies used to raise financial and social resources; reflect on how communication and discourse influence the acceptance of new ideas; apply concepts from institutional theory to understand the dynamics of the organizational field.</p>
<p>The NGO "Ação Educativa" addresses the issue of educational quality in São Paulo's public schools, highlighting the need for innovation and change in educational practices.</p>	<p>The case can be used to discuss topics such as social innovation, institutional entrepreneurship, and the importance of active participation in education. Students can analyze the challenges faced by the NGO and reflect on how these experiences can be applied to their own educational contexts.</p>	<p>Understand the importance of innovation in education and the role of NGOs; discuss the NGO's practices, school management simulations, and reflections on student participation; analyze the testimonies of the participants and propose solutions to the educational problems identified in the case.</p>

Source: Research data (2024).

In both case studies, the entrepreneurial process is evidenced by the mobilization of resources and the implementation of strategies that promote organizational transformation and social impact. At COPAGRIL, the construction of a poultry complex demonstrates how collective action, board legitimacy, and the construction of meaning helped overcome financial challenges and diversify activities. In the case of the NGO "Ação Educativa," social innovation and the

active participation of students and teachers reveal how institutional entrepreneurship can transform educational practices.

In the classroom, collective work, resource mobilization, and the construction of meaning in institutional entrepreneurship can be discussed. Teaching notes can include analysis of the roles of social actors, fundraising strategies, and school management simulations, encouraging students to reflect on the practice of entrepreneurship in cooperative and educational contexts.

Chart 10: Case study in religious entrepreneurship religioso

Article No. and Case Study Summary	Classroom Use	Teaching Notes
<p>9 Religious entrepreneurship, focusing on companies that sell faith-related items in the cities of Uberlândia, Uberaba, and Araguari, in the Triângulo Mineiro region.</p>	<p>The case study can be used to discuss topics such as entrepreneurship, innovation in unconventional contexts, and the intersection of religion and business.</p>	<p>Analyze how knowledge and experience in a specific niche can lead to the identification of opportunities; reflect on how these companies influence their communities and promote religiosity; and explore how different religious traditions can coexist and impact the market.</p>

Source: Research data (2024).

The case study demonstrates how entrepreneurs in the Triângulo Mineiro region used their knowledge and socialization within faith communities to identify and explore business opportunities, such as religious articles. The case highlights the importance of religious experience and syncretism in creating a specific market for products such as books and religious objects.

In the classroom, specialization in niche markets and the intersection between entrepreneurship and religious practices can be discussed. Teaching notes can include an analysis of opportunities in specific niches, reflection on the social impact of religious entrepreneurship, and exploration of syncretism in the market, providing students with a deeper understanding of how cultural and religious knowledge can influence business success.

Chart 11: Case studies in technological entrepreneurship

Article No. and Case Study Summary	Classroom Use	Teaching Notes
<p>11</p> <p>The problem of growth for small software companies in Paraná and Santa Catarina, highlighting the difficulties and determinants that influence this process.</p>	<p>The case study can be used to discuss topics such as entrepreneurship, innovation, human resource management, and growth strategies.</p>	<p>Study market conditions and how companies can adapt to a competitive environment; reflect on the importance of skills beyond technical knowledge for business success; discuss how innovation can be a driver for growth and customer retention; and explore the importance of support networks and partnerships for small business development.</p>
<p>18</p> <p>The problem of independent inventors in Brazil, highlighting their importance in the patent system and technological innovation.</p>	<p>The case study can be used to discuss topics such as innovation, entrepreneurship, and public policy. Students can analyze the situation of independent inventors in Brazil and compare it with that of other countries, fostering debates on the importance of government and private support for innovation.</p>	<p>Understand the importance of independent inventors and the challenges they face; conduct group discussions, analyze patent data, and research innovation policies in other countries; and present public policy proposals that could support independent inventors in Brazil.</p>
<p>23</p> <p>Mobilization of relationships and access to resources by two entrepreneurs during the creation of their companies.</p>	<p>This case can be used to discuss topics such as entrepreneurship, relationship networks, and the importance of social capital. Students can analyze how different types of resources (physical, financial, social, and organizational) impact the development of new businesses.</p>	<p>Promote a discussion on the importance of relationship networks in entrepreneurship; ask students to identify and compare Marcelo's and Eduardo's strategies for mobilizing resources; and ask students to write a short essay on how their own relationship networks can influence their future entrepreneurial initiatives.</p>

Source: Research data (2024).

The three case studies offer insights into various aspects of entrepreneurship, from the growth of small software companies to innovation and the importance of networks. The study of software company growth reveals challenges such as the lack of managerial skills and the need for institutional support, making it useful for discussing management training, innovation strategies, and the role of networking. The case of independent inventors highlights difficulties in accessing venture capital and the importance of public

policies that encourage innovation. Finally, the case of mobilizing relationships demonstrates how networks impact access to resources and business development, allowing students to leverage social capital as a competitive differentiator.

In the classroom, students can analyze these cases to better understand the practice of entrepreneurship and reflect on how to apply these concepts to their own experiences, with teaching notes addressing managerial skills, innovation policies, and the role of networks.

Chart 12: Case study in educational entrepreneurship

Article No. and Case Study Summary	Classroom Use	Teaching Notes
<p>12 Effectiveness of entrepreneurship training activities (AEFE) in transforming the profile of university students.</p>	<p>This case study can be used in the classroom to promote discussions about the importance of entrepreneurship education and teaching methodologies.</p>	<p>It can encourage students to reflect on the effectiveness of different entrepreneurship teaching methodologies; promote discussions about the characteristics of entrepreneurs and how they can be developed; and analyze the practical application of entrepreneurship training activities and their impact on student profiles.</p>

Source: Research data (2024).

The case study highlights the challenge of transforming the profile of university students through entrepreneurship training activities (EAPs). Research with Business Administration students in Fortaleza reveals the need for effective methods for teaching and assessing entrepreneurial traits.

In the classroom, the effectiveness of different teaching methodologies can be explored, discussions can be fostered about the development of entrepreneurial traits, and the impact of EAPs on student development can be analyzed. Teaching notes can include critical analyses of the methodologies, discussions about the entrepreneurial profile, and case studies of educational activities, fostering a deeper and more critical understanding of entrepreneurship education and its implications for student development.

Chart 13: Case study in innovative entrepreneurship

Article No. and Case Study Summary	Classroom Use	Teaching Notes
<p>16 Addresses the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and open innovation in Brazilian startups.</p>	<p>The case study can be used in entrepreneurship, innovation, and startup management classes. Students can discuss the importance of open innovation and how it can be applied in different contexts.</p>	<p>Promote discussions on the advantages and disadvantages of open innovation for startups; study other examples of startups that have successfully implemented open innovation practices; encourage students to create open innovation proposals for a fictitious startup, considering market challenges and opportunities.</p>

Source: Research data (2024).

This case study explores the connection between entrepreneurial orientation and open innovation in Brazilian startups, focusing on Company A of Santa Rita do Sapucaí, known as "Electronic Valley." The case illustrates how open innovation, which involves collaboration and access to external resources, is crucial for startup growth and innovation.

In the classroom, the practical application of open innovation and its impact on startup development can be discussed, fostering debate about its advantages and disadvantages. Teaching notes can include group discussions, analysis of similar cases, and the development of open innovation proposals for fictitious startups, allowing students to better understand the theory and practice of open innovation and fostering creativity and critical thinking.

Chart 14: Case study in international entrepreneurship

Article No. and Case Study Summary	Classroom Use	Teaching Notes
<p>17 The problem of internationalization of agribusiness companies, specifically in the fruit sector, highlighting the risks faced during this process.</p>	<p>The case study can be used to discuss topics such as international entrepreneurship, risk management, and adaptation strategies in challenging environments.</p>	<p>Understand the challenges of internationalization and the importance of risk management; analyze the decisions made by Agro Melão's managers and their implications; apply entrepreneurship and risk management theories to practical situations faced by the company; encourage students to propose alternative solutions to the challenges identified in the case study.</p>

Source: Research data (2024).

The case study explores the challenges of internationalization in the fruit industry, highlighting risks related to exchange rates, climate conditions, and adjustments to the global market. Located in the Brazilian semiarid region, the company faced economic crises and adapted its strategies between 1997 and 2012.

In the classroom, international entrepreneurship and risk management can be discussed, allowing students to analyze how the company faced these challenges. Teaching notes can include defining objectives focused on the risks of internationalization, discussing Agro Melão's decisions, and case studies applying risk management theories, promoting critical reflection and proposing alternative solutions to business challenges.

Chart 15: Case study in digital entrepreneurship

Article No. and Case Study Summary	Classroom Use	Teaching Notes
<p>19 Creation of a technology-based company focused on managing websites for small businesses.</p>	<p>The case study can be used to discuss topics such as the resource-based view (RBV), the importance of planning in new businesses, and the dynamics of startups.</p>	<p>Analyze how a company's resources can be used to gain a competitive advantage; explore the importance of planning in the early stages of a business and how this can impact the company's survival; discuss the challenges faced by startups in dynamic environments and the need for constant adaptation.</p>

Source: Research data (2024).

The case study explores the challenges faced in configuring strategic resources in a dynamic startup environment. The company aims to facilitate the creation and maintenance of websites for small businesses with an intuitive platform, emphasizing the importance of strategic planning and resource identification for sustainable competitive advantage.

In the classroom, the Resource-Based View (RBV) can be explored, strategic planning in the early stages discussed, and startup dynamics analyzed. Teaching notes can include discussions on how resources contribute to competitive advantage, the importance of strategic planning, and the challenges

of startups in dynamic environments, promoting the practical application of the theories discussed.

Chart 16: Case study in small firms' entrepreneurship

Article No. and Case Study Summary	Classroom Use	Teaching Notes
<p>21</p> <p>The problem of business opportunity evaluation by entrepreneurs in emerging markets, focusing on risk perception and the cognitive biases that influence this evaluation.</p>	<p>The case can be used to discuss the importance of critical analysis in entrepreneurial decision-making, addressing how cognitive biases can affect risk perception.</p>	<p>Explore how different biases, such as the Law of Small Numbers and the Planning Fallacy, impact entrepreneurial decisions; encourage students to consider the importance of representative data in opportunity evaluation; compare students' experiences with those of the entrepreneurs in the study, promoting reflection on their own decisions and risk perceptions.</p>

Source: Research data (2024).

The case study examines how micro and small business entrepreneurs in Brazil face challenges related to risk perception and cognitive biases, such as the Law of Small Numbers and the Planning Fallacy. The study highlights that entrepreneurial decisions are often based on personal experiences and unrepresentative anecdotes rather than solid statistical data.

In the classroom, the importance of critical analysis and the impact of cognitive biases on decision-making can be discussed. Teaching notes can explore how these biases influence decisions, the importance of representative data, and comparisons with real-world experiences, encouraging reflection on students' decisions and risk perception.

Chart 17: Case study in immigrant entrepreneurship

Article No. and Case Study Summary	Classroom Use	Teaching Notes
<p>25</p> <p>Experiences of 19 Brazilian entrepreneurs who established startups in Canada, focusing on the barriers, difficulties, and opportunities they faced.</p>	<p>The case study can be used to discuss topics such as entrepreneurship, internationalization, innovation, and the specificities of immigrant entrepreneurship.</p>	<p>Study the barriers faced by immigrant entrepreneurs and how to overcome them; discuss the Uppsala model and its application in startup contexts; identify and analyze the strategies that led to the startups' success, promoting a debate on innovation and market adaptation.</p>

Source: Research data (2024).

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The case study illustrates the challenges and opportunities of immigrant entrepreneurship, highlighting adaptation to a new cultural and market context. Facing barriers related to flexible planning, social networks, and human capital, they applied the Uppsala model to internationalization.

In the classroom, the challenges of immigrant entrepreneurship, internationalization strategies, and innovation can be discussed. Teaching notes can include analyzing the barriers faced, applying the Uppsala model, and identifying successful strategies, fostering discussions on innovation and market adaptation. These activities help students understand the complexities of international entrepreneurship and develop skills to face similar challenges.

CONCLUSION

The present research aimed to analyze the educational practices present in case studies, assessing how they impact the development of entrepreneurial competencies and their relationship with the entrepreneurial process. The analyses revealed a diversity of approaches and themes, highlighting the richness of the entrepreneurship field and the importance of an education that goes beyond theory by incorporating practical experiences and real-world contexts.

The main contributions of this research include the identification of effective educational practices that promote the development of entrepreneurial skills such as critical analysis, problem-solving, and the ability to adapt to new situations. The case studies analyzed - covering areas such as female, technological, social, and digital entrepreneurship - offer concrete examples that can be used in the classroom to illustrate theoretical concepts and stimulate meaningful discussions. The teaching notes associated with these cases serve as guides for educators, enabling structured debates and helping achieve educational objectives effectively.

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Furthermore, the research highlighted gaps in the literature, suggesting the need for more studies that integrate theory and practice, especially in emerging areas of entrepreneurship. By providing a comprehensive view of the intersection between education and entrepreneurship, this article not only enriches the academic debate but also offers practical guidelines for educators and policymakers. In doing so, it contributes to the preparation of entrepreneurs who are better equipped for the challenges of the contemporary market, while promoting a pedagogical approach that values practical experience and critical reflection.

For future research, it is suggested to investigate the effectiveness of innovative methodologies, such as project-based teaching and experiential learning, in developing entrepreneurial competencies in different educational contexts. Another aspect to be considered is the integration of soft skills, such as leadership and communication, into the entrepreneurial education curriculum, evaluating how these skills can be fostered through case studies. Finally, conducting longitudinal studies to assess the impact of entrepreneurial education on the professional trajectories of alumni may provide a deeper understanding of how the competencies acquired influence their careers and business initiatives.

REFERENCES

AKOBENG, A.K. Understanding systematic reviews and meta-analysis. **Archives of Disease in Childhood**, v.90, n.8, p.845–848, 2005.

BARBIERI, J.C. Os inventores no Brasil: tipos e modalidades de incentivos. **RAE-Revista de Administração de Empresas**, São Paulo, v.39, n.2, p.54-63, 1999.

RELISE

BARBIERI, J.C. **Estudos de casos**: uma proposta de ensino. São Paulo: Atlas, 2005.

BORGES, A.F.; ENOQUE, A.G.; BORGES, J.F. Empreendedorismo religioso: um estudo sobre empresas que exploram o nicho da religiosidade. **RAC-Revista de Administração Contemporânea**, Rio de Janeiro, v.19, n.5, p. 565-583, 2015.

BRUSTEIN, J.; RODRIGUES, A.L.; KIRSCHBAUM, C. Inovação social e empreendedorismo institucional: a ação da ONG “Ação educativa” no campo educacional da cidade de São Paulo. **O&S-Organizações e Sociedade**, v.15, n.46 - Jul/Set, p.119-136, 2008.

CARVALHO, E.G.; SUGANO, J.Y. Entrepreneurial orientation and open innovation in brazilian startups: a multicase study. **Interações**, Campo Grande, MS, v.17, n.3, p. 448-462, jul./set., 2016.

CORRÊA, V.S.; VALE, G.M.V. Redes sociais, perfil empreendedor e trajetórias. **RAUSP-Revista de Administração de São Paulo**, São Paulo, v.49, n.1, p.77-88, 2014.

CORRÊA, V.S.; VALE, G.M.V.; PINTO, M.R. Social Coupling and Decoupling: pastors as entrepreneurs. **RAE-Revista de Administração de Empresas (Journal of Business Management)**, v.58, n.2, p. 188-200, 2018.

CUNHA, V.B.C.; NASCIMENTO, T.C.; FALCÃO, R.P.Q. In search of an integrative framework for female immigrant entrepreneurship. **RAE-Revista de Administração de Empresas**, v.64, n.1, p.1-25, e2022-0469, 2024.

RELISE

237

DOLABELA, Fernando. **O Segredo de Luísa**: Uma ideia, uma paixão, e um plano de negócios – como nasce o empreendedor e se cria uma empresa. 31 ed. Rio de Janeiro: Sextante, 2008.

DORNELAS, J.C.A. **Empreendedorismo**: Transformando Ideias em Negócios. 6 ed. Rio de Janeiro: Elsevier, 2018.

DRUCKER, P.F. **Innovation and Entrepreneurship**: Practice and Principles. New York: Harper & Row, 1985.

FALCÃO, R.P.Q.; MACHADO, M.M.; CRUZ, E.P.; CUNHA, R.M. Trajetórias emergentes de startups brasileiras-canadenses à luz do Modelo de Uppsala, empreendedorismo de imigrantes e da effectuation. **REAd-Revista Eletrônica de Administração**, v.27, n.3, p.835-869, 2021.

FERREIRA, K.F.O.; GUIMARÃES, L.O.; SALUME, P.K.; DOYLE, M.L.F.C.P. Analysis of the entrepreneurial process form effectuation and causation logic: a case study in two companies from Minas Gerais. **Revista de Administração da UFSM**, Santa Maria, v.15, n.1, p.83-104, 2022.

FILION, L.J. **O Processo Empreendedor**. São Paulo: Makron Books, 1999.

FLICK, U. **Desenho da pesquisa qualitativa**. Porto Alegre: Artmed, 2009.

FONSECA, F.; NASSIF, M.E. Informação e empreendedorismo: estudos de caso com acadêmicos brasileiros e canadenses. **Perspectivas em Ciência da Informação**, v.27, n.4, p.167-195, 2022.

RELISE

238

GIBB, A.A. In pursuit of a new 'enterprise' and 'entrepreneurship' paradigm for learning: Creative destruction, new values, new ways of doing things and new combinations of knowledge. **International Journal of Management Reviews**, v.4, n.3, p.233-269, 2002.

GOMES, R.K.; EMMENDOERFER, M.L. Intraempreendedorismo e inovação em organizações públicas: caso do censo no Brasil. **Estudos Avançados**, v.37, n.109, p.361-380, 2023.

HISRICH, R.D.; PETERS, M.P.; SHEPHERD, D.A. **Empreendedorismo**. 9 ed. Porto Alegre: AMGH, 2014.

JONES, C. **Teaching entrepreneurship to undergraduates**. Edward Elgar Publishing, 2011.

KLANDT, H. (2004). Entrepreneurship education and research in German-speaking Europe. **Frontiers of Entrepreneurship Research**. Babson College, p.718-728, 2004.

LAPOLLI, E.M.; GOMES, R.K. Práticas intraempreendedoras na gestão pública: um estudo de caso na Embrapa. **Estudos avançados**, V.31, N.90, P.127-142, 2017.

LEITE, Y.V.P.; MORAES, W.F.A. Facetas do Risco no Empreendedorismo Internacional. **RAC-Revista de Administração Contemporânea**, v.18, n.1, p.96-117, 2014.

RELISE

239

MACHADO, H.P.V.; GAZOLA, S.; ANEZ, M.E.M. Criação de empresas por mulheres: um estudo com empreendedoras em Natal, Rio Grande do Norte. **RAM-Revista de Administração Mackenzie**, v.14, n.5, p.177-200, 2013.

MACHADO, H.P.V. Crescimento de Empresas na Perspectiva de Pequenos Empreendedores de Base Tecnológica. **RAC-Revista de Administração Contemporânea**, v.22, n.6, p.817-840, 2018.

MARCHAND, P.; RATINAUD, P. L'analyse de similitude appliquée aux corpus textuels: les primaires socialistes pour l'élection présidentielle française. In **Actes des 11eme Journées internationales d'Analyse statistique des Données Textuelles**. JADT 2012, p.687-699, 2012.

MASSA, R.M.; ANDREASSI, T.; PARTYKA, R.B.; LANA, J. Opportunity or Illusion? Risk Perception in Opportunity Evaluation. **BBR-Brazilian Business Review**, v.21, n.2, p.1-24, 2024.

MEDEIROS JÚNIOR, J.V.; AÑEZ, M.E.M.; SOUSA NETO, M.V.; BEZERRA, M.H.M. Elaboração do mapa de recursos: processo de apoio ao planejamento de um novo negócio de internet. **RAM-Revista de Administração Mackenzie**, v.16, n.5, p.226-256, 2015.

MORRIS, M. H.; LIGUORI, E. Teaching entrepreneurship as a method: A new approach to teaching the core of entrepreneurship. **Journal of Entrepreneurship Education**, v.19, n.2, p.60-71, 2016.

RELISE

240

RAE, D. Connecting enterprise and graduate employability: Challenges to the higher education culture and curriculum? **Education & Training**, v.49, n.8/9, p.605-619, 2007.

ROCHA, E.L.C.; FREITAS, A.A.F. Avaliação do Ensino de Empreendedorismo entre Estudantes Universitários por meio do Perfil Empreendedor. **RAC-Revista de Administração Contemporânea**, v.18, n.4, p.465-486, 2014.

RODRIGUES, A.L.; MALO, M.C. Estruturas de governança e empreendedorismo coletivo: o caso dos doutores da alegria. **RAC-Revista de Administração Contemporânea**, v.10, n.3, p. 29-50, 2006.

ROSSONI, L.; TEIXEIRA, R.M. A interação dos relacionamentos com os recursos e a legitimidade no processo de criação de uma organização social. **Cadernos EBAPE.BR**, v.6, n.4, p.1-19, 2008.

SANDER, J.A.; CUNHA, C.R. Atores sociais e campo organizacional: estratégias discursivas e de mobilização de recursos na construção do complexo avícola na cooperativa agroindustrial Copagril. **RAM-Revista de Administração Mackenzie**, v.14, n.4, p.189-221, 2013.

SEVERINO, A.J. **Metodologia do trabalho científico**. 23 ed. São Paulo: Cortez, 2007.

SHANE, S.; VENKATARAMAN, S. The promise of entrepreneurship as a field of research. **Academy of Management Review**, v. 25, n.1, p.217-226, 2000.

RELISE

241

TEIXEIRA, R.M.; ANDREASSI, T.; BOMFIM, L.C.S. Use of entrepreneurial social networks by women in the travel agencies creation process. **Revista Brasileira de Pesquisa em Turismo**, v.12, n.1, p.102-132, 2018.

TIMMONS, J.A.; SPINELLI, S. **New Venture Creation: Entrepreneurship for the 21st Century** (8th ed.). McGraw-Hill/Irwin, 2007.

TRANFIELD, D.; DENYER, D.; SMART, P. (2003). Towards a Methodology for Developing Evidence Informed Management Knowledge by Means of Systematic Review. **British Journal of Management**, v.14, n.3, p.207–222, 2003.

VALADARES, J. L.; EMMENDOERFER, M.L. Cargos de Livre Nomeação: Reflexões com Base no Empreendedor Público em um Estado-Membro do Brasil. **RAC-Revista de Administração Contemporânea**, v.16, n.5, p.723-743, 2012.

VALE, G.M.V.; SERAFIM, A.C.F.; TEODÓSIO, A.S.S. Gênero, Imersão e Empreendedorismo: Sexo Frágil, Laços Fortes? **RAC-Revista de Administração Contemporânea**, v.15, n.4, p.631-649, 2011.

VASCONCELOS, G.M.R.; REZENDE, S.F.L.; GUIMARÃES, L.O.; FACHIN, R.C. Mobilizando relacionamentos e acessando recursos na criação e evolução de novos negócios. **O&S-Organizações e Sociedade**, v.14, n.41, p.113-134, 2007.

YIN, R.K. **Case Study Research and Applications: Design and Methods**. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, 2018.